

Victims and Memory Politics

The Role of Former Political Prisoners in Shaping Memorial Landscapes in the Czech Republic and Germany

Klára Pinerová

Paper presented at the conference: Power and Control of Society in Communist Regimes, Tirana, 22-23 October 2025

Available at: [| Extractive Zones \(cs\)](#)

After 1989, organizations of victims of the communist dictatorship began to emerge or expand in Czechoslovakia and Germany and soon became important actors in transitional justice. They advocated for rehabilitation and reparations, demanded the punishment of those responsible for violence and persecution, and also promoted their view of the recent past. Although the two states share a common experience of state socialism, their ways of dealing with this past and creating ‘sites of memory’ differ fundamentally in many ways. While in Germany the memory of the victims has become part of large-scale, state-sponsored memorial policies, in the Czech Republic the victims, especially through their organisation the

Confederation of Political Prisoners, have for a long time become the main initiators of museum and memorial projects.

The political and social context after 1989

In the Czech Republic, the revolutionary change in 1989 was associated with demands for a rapid moral and legal cleansing of society. Rehabilitation and lustration laws were passed, and in 1993 the Law on the Illegality of the Communist Regime was also adopted, declaratively condemning the communist dictatorship as “criminal, illegitimate and despicable”. The field of memory remained largely unregulated and decentralized. This provided a wide space for victims, especially the Confederation, which became the main spokesperson for the victims of the communist dictatorship.

In Germany, by contrast, unification meant incorporating the new federal states into the existing democratic tradition of the Federal Republic. Memory policy was linked to parliamentary commissions (Enquête-Kommissionen Aufarbeitung von Geschichte und Folgen der SED-Diktatur in Deutschland) and extensive state support programmes. In 1998, on the basis of the recommendations of these parliamentary commissions, the Bundesstiftung zur Aufarbeitung der SED-Diktatur was established to fund research and memory projects. The victims had a voice here, but always within the framework of a state-controlled discourse.

Victims’ organisations as actors of memory

In the Czech environment, the Confederation of Political Prisoners, founded in 1990, has been a key actor in promoting the interests of imprisoned victims of the communist dictatorship. Its goals went beyond the mere care of former prisoners, as it sought not only moral satisfaction and recognition of their role in the fall of the dictatorship, but also legal recognition of the anti-communist resistance.

In West Germany, there were still a number of associations before 1989, whose activities expanded to new territories after 1989, while new associations were created to bring together victims on a local level or according to the type of repression. The associations were in competition and there were disputes between them. The result was a fragmentation of demands and an inconsistent narrative. All this led to their lobby not being as successful as in the Czech Republic. Among the most important associations was the Vereinigung der Opfer des Stalinismus (VOS), founded as early as 1950 in West Berlin. Due to the fragmentation of the associations, the Union der Opferverbände Kommunistischer Gewaltherrschaft (UOKG) was founded in 1992, which represents the various victim associations. These organisations had access to political decision-making processes, but at the same time had to submit to the logic of the institutional politics of memory.

These different initial conditions led to the formation of two different “memory cultures”. In the Czech Republic, a “spontaneous” memory culture developed, which was based on authentic testimonies, was highly emotional, and often lacked professional museum processing. The result was a number of memorials and museums with unique artefacts, but with limited attendance and often without a professional concept. In Germany, however, an

“institutionalized” memory culture developed, which was built systematically, with professional museum practice and state support, but often in conflict with victims who felt marginalized and “supervised” by historians

Czech Republic: victims as the main creators of memory space

In the Czech environment after 1989, the victims of the communist dictatorship became the main drivers of memory initiatives. The Confederation of Political Prisoners played the biggest role in this respect. While the state has long focused more on the legislative and social aspects of coming to terms with the past (rehabilitation, restitution, compensation), the space of memory has remained largely open. This allowed it to be filled for a long time by victims and their organisations.

One of the most significant projects of the Confederation was the establishment of the Museum of the Third Resistance in Příbram. The idea for its creation emerged immediately after the political prisoners failed to pass a law on the recognition of the anti-communist resistance. The museum was created mainly on the initiative of former prisoners themselves, who donated valuable personal objects, documents and memoirs. From the beginning, the exhibition was characterized by a strong emotional emphasis and direct authenticity. Professional museum and historical work was rather in the background. In the 1990s, the museum expanded, and new exhibitions devoted to the imprisonment of women and the Soviet Gulag were created. Nevertheless, it remained a rather local institution with limited attendance. After 2000, the problem of generational change became apparent: the museum was still run by former prisoners who were getting older and gradually leaving. The town of Příbram finally stopped providing premises in 2021 and the museum effectively ceased to exist. The unique collection of objects is now defunct. This case shows the limits of “spontaneously founded” institutions. Their creation is possible thanks to extraordinary personal commitment, but their long-term survival requires an institutional background that has long been lacking in the Czech environment.

Another example where the initiative of the victims was combined with the action of the state is the War Memorial, a former labour camp. It is part of the Mining Museum, a state institution. Members of the Confederation also played a significant role in the creation of the exhibition. In one of the rooms, the so-called chapel, there is a large cross and a list of 247 executed persons. The accompanying text explicitly notes that among them are “those who morally do not belong here”, i.e. communists condemned as part of the purges of power. This detail illustrates well how the victims asserted their own interpretation of the past, in which only anti-communists were the ‘real martyrs’. A large part of the exhibition is also devoted to anti-communist resistance. The memorial bears traces not only of historical documentation but also of the victims’ value judgments.

It is only in recent years that the state has become involved in the creation of new museums and memorials. Currently, a memorial is being prepared on the premises of the former remand prison in Uherské Hradiště, which is notorious for the abuse of political prisoners during interrogation. The memorial was initiated by the Memoria Association, which opposed the commercial use of the building. Thanks to their activities, the Museum of Totalitarianism is

due to open here in 2028. The Memoria Society is striving to make the prison a National Memorial to the Victims of Totalitarian Regimes.

Similarly, the “Red Tower of Death” building, located in the Jáchymov region, was the site of prison labour camps at the uranium mines, which became a symbol of political repression and the harsh living conditions to which prisoners were subjected. The building has long been a national cultural monument. Since 2008, it has been owned by the Confederation, which, however, did not have the funding to build the memorial. In 2022, a collaboration between the Confederation and the Institute for the Study of Totalitarian Regimes created an award-winning exhibit commemorating the lives of prisoners in the labour camps. It was the first steps to list the building as a place of memory and to open part of the site to the public. In 2025, the building was handed over to the state, which is now preparing the groundwork for the establishment of the memorial.

These examples show that Czech memory culture after 1989 was strongly victim-led. This brought several positives: unique collections, authentic exhibitions and places of intense memory value were created. At the same time, however, a chain of limitations became apparent, such as the lack of professionalisation. Exhibitions often became outdated, systematic management and marketing were lacking, and visitor numbers were low. There was a heavy reliance on individuals, as institutional facilities disappeared with the death of memorials.

Germany: the memory of state socialism in an institutional framework

In contrast to the Czech Republic, where victims became the main initiators of memory projects, German developments after 1989 show the opposite trend. Here, the state played a crucial role, investing heavily in the construction of memorials and museums after reunification. In this context, victims became partners but also opponents of state institutions and historians. The field of memory in Germany was shaped from the outset by two tensions, namely the competition between the memory of the Nazi and socialist dictatorships and the conflict between the testimony of victims and historical interpretation. In the 1990s, Germany created a systematic network of ‘Gedenkstätten’ that included sites associated with Nazi crimes as well as, more recently, with the SED dictatorship.

The former Stasi remand prison Hohenschönhausen in Berlin became a symbol of the new memory culture. Its creation was strongly influenced by former prisoners who became guides through the premises and offered authentic testimony. Under the leadership of Hubert Knabe (2001-2018), the memorial gained a great deal of political influence, but historians and museum workers have criticized the memorial for becoming a “moral tribunal” instead of an educational institution. After Knabe’s dismissal in 2018, the leadership has sought a more balanced approach between victim testimony and critical historical context.

Similarly, at Bautzen, the site of the prison, former prisoners played a significant role in shaping the memorial. Their insistence on emphasizing suffering often clashed with historians’ desire to offer visitors a broader picture of repression in Germany, as historians

advocated a pluralistic view encompassing all phases of repression (Soviet camps, the GDR, and the postwar period).

A specific situation occurred at Sachsenhausen, a former Nazi concentration camp that was used as a Soviet special camp after 1945. The memory of Nazi crimes has long been dominant here. After 1990, victims of Soviet and East German repression claimed their place, sparking sensitive debates about the hierarchy of victims and the risk of relativising the Holocaust. Historians advocated an integrated, contextualized approach that emphasized the historical continuity of violence and the abuse of place. This approach was initially perceived by the victims as relativizing their suffering, but gradually became an accepted model, not least because of the high level of expertise in the exhibits.

Another example is the Cottbus Memorial, where the former prison building was taken over by former political prisoners at the Menschenrechtszentrum Cottbus after protests against plans to convert the prison into a commercial building. The memorial was built from below, without initial state support, and only gradually gained recognition and financial support. The victims themselves operate the memorial, but they also recognize the need to adhere to museological standards to ensure credibility and funding. The exhibit combines personal stories with historical context and human rights themes, linking the past to current issues of freedom and surveillance. This approach combines both emotional testimony and a professional framework.

In contrast to the Czech Republic, the German debate on the memory of the SED-dictatorship was shaped from the beginning by the confrontation with the memory of the Holocaust. Victims of communism have often faced accusations of relativizing Nazi crimes. Conservative circles, on the other hand, stressed the parallel between the “two dictatorships” and promoted the concept of “totalitarianism” as a common framework. This discourse was reflected in the work of the parliamentary commissions of inquiry (Enquete-Kommissionen), which sought to define the official position on the history of the GDR. The result was the recognition of the victims and their reparations, but also a certain hierarchisation that in practice left the Holocaust at the top of the “memory pyramid”.

An important motif in the German context is the sense of so-called double victimization. Many former Stasi prisoners described how, although they were rehabilitated after 1990, their suffering was not sufficiently acknowledged by society or the state. Psychological studies show that this lack of social validation led to a deepening of the trauma, a sense of victim uselessness and lasting bitterness. The victims thus found themselves in a paradoxical situation: the state provided them with memorials and financial compensation, but they themselves often felt marginalised. This explains their intense efforts to promote their own narratives in museums and memorials.

Comparison: two memory models

A comparison of Czech and German memory culture after 1989 shows two different trajectories, which depended on the political and institutional framework, but also on the historical experience of both societies. In both countries, victims and their organizations were

active actors and sought to create “places of memory” where their memory would be preserved and transmitted. In both countries, however, victims had very different conditions. While in the Czech Republic there was still no state concept, in Germany there was strong state support. This led to victims being in a completely different position. In the Czech Republic, the victims were the main initiators of the expositions and the state was often only put in the position of creating a memorial under public pressure. In Germany, the victims were more likely to be partners or critics of professional institutions. All of this also affected the durability of memorial sites, as in the Czech Republic some of them are threatened with extinction, whereas in Germany these institutions are financially and professionally stable. Last but not least, there are different cultural and memory conditions in both countries. While in Germany there is a constant confrontation with the memory of the Holocaust, in the Czech Republic this framework is completely absent.

The article is based on the project "Political Polarisation and Communist Past: the Czech and German Case" No. 101109026, conducted at the Technical University of Dresden.

OpenEdition suggests that you cite this post as follows:

Klára Pinerová (November 5, 2025). Victims and Memory Politics. *Recognizing Victimhood*. Retrieved January 7, 2026 from <https://popolacop.hypotheses.org/475>